

Effectiveness of tap water versus warm water foot soak on the level of fatigue among patients after hemodialysis at selected hospitals

Ms. Rasika Rajesh Tambe^{1*}, Mrs. Swati Gorad²

1. *Specialty Medical Surgical Nursing [CVTN], Sinhgad college of nursing*

2. *Designation Lecturer, Sinhgad college of nursing*

Received: Aug 27, 2025

Accepted: Sep 25, 2025

Published: Sep 26, 2025

ABSTRACT: -

INTRODUCTION: This study investigates the effectiveness of tap water versus warm water foot soak on the level of fatigue among patients after hemodialysis at selected hospitals.

METHOD: - The research methodology adopted for the study was the quantitative research approach. The investigator used the true experimental, parallel-group design. The study was based on the Wiedenbachs prescriptive theory. The accessible population selected for this study consisted of patients diagnosed with chronic kidney disease, acute kidney disease, and those who were available during the study at the selected hospitals. The sample size was 60 (experimental group I 30, experimental group II 30) and were selected as per the inclusion criteria using the Probability, Simple random sampling technique. The tool consists of demographic data and a self-structured fatigue assessment scale.

RESULT: -

Section I: Description of sample based on demographic data.

Demographic Data collected of the samples regarding Age, Gender, Occupation, Personal habits, Healthy habits, Diagnosis, Hemodialysis session in a week, Duration of hemodialysis session.

Section II : Findings related to the level of fatigue before the implementation of tap water and warm water among patients undergoing hemodialysis at selected hospitals

In Tap water group, 83.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue and 16.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis. In warm water group, 73.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue and 26.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis.

Section III : Findings related to the effectiveness of tap water foot soak on the level of fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis at selected hospitals.

In Tap water group 83.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue and 16.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis. In posttest, all of them had moderate fatigue after hemodialysis. This indicates that the fatigue among patients improved remarkably after tap water foot soak.

Findings related to effectiveness of warm water foot soak on pretest and post-test level of fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

In warm water group 73.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue, and 26.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis. In the post-test, 76.7 of them had Moderate fatigue, and 23.3% of them had mild fatigue after hemodialysis. This indicates that the fatigue among patients improved remarkably after a warm water foot soak.

Section IV : Findings related to the paired t-test for the effectiveness of tap water foot soak on the pretest and post-test level of fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

The researcher applied a paired t-test for the effectiveness of tap water foot soak on fatigue among patients after hemodialysis. The average fatigue score in the pretest was 72.7, which was reduced to 66.8 in the posttest. The t-value for this test was 19.9 with 29 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), so the null hypothesis was rejected.

Findings related to Paired t-test for the effectiveness of warm water foot soak on the fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

The researcher applied a paired t-test for the effectiveness of warm water foot soak on fatigue among patients after hemodialysis. The average fatigue score in the pretest was 71.9, which was reduced to 58.6 in the posttest. The t-value for this test was 24, with 29 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The warm water foot soak is significantly effective in reducing fatigue among patients after hemodialysis.

Findings related to two sample z-tests for the comparison of the effectiveness of tap water foot soak and warm water foot soak on fatigue among patients after hemodialysis.

The researcher applied two sample t-tests for the comparison of the effectiveness of warm water foot soak and tap water foot soak on fatigue among patients after hemodialysis. The average reduction in fatigue score in the tap water foot soak group was 5.9, which was 13.4 in the warm water foot soak group. The Z-value for this test was 11.9. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average reduction in fatigue score is significantly more in the warm water foot soak group than in the tap water foot soak group. The warm water foot soak is significantly more effective than the tap water foot soak in reducing fatigue among patients after hemodialysis.

Section V: Findings related to the comparison of the effectiveness of tap water foot soak and warm water foot soak on fatigue among patients after hemodialysis.

In Tap water group 83.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue and 16.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis. In posttest, all of them had moderate fatigue after hemodialysis.

In warm water group, 73.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue and 26.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis. In posttest, 76.7 of them had moderate fatigue and 23.3% of them had mild fatigue after hemodialysis. This indicates that the fatigue among patients improved remarkably after warm water foot soak as compared to tap water.

Section VI: Analysis of data related to the association of fatigue with the selected demographic variable

Fisher's exact test was used for the association between fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis with the demographical variables.

Since p-value corresponding to healthy habits was small (less than 0.05), the demographic variable healthy habits were found to have significant association with the fatigue among hemodialysis patients.

CONCLUSION: -The study aimed to assess the effectiveness of tap water and warm water foot soak on the level of fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

KEYWORDS: -

Tap water foot soak, warm water foot soak, Hemodialysis, Fatigue, and self-structured Fatigue assessment scale.

INTRODUCTION:

Dialysis is a procedure used on people whose kidneys are not working.

Well enough. Renal failure results in insufficient blood filtration by the kidneys. As a result, wastes and poisons accumulate in the blood. As the kidneys, the dialysis machine purges the blood of waste and surplus fluid. There are two types of dialysis: hemodialysis and peritoneal dialysis. Hemodialysis is the process of taking blood out of the body, filtering it with a dialyzer, and then putting it back in. These three to four-hour treatments could take place in a hospital or a dialysis center twice a week.[1]

Peritoneum dialysis is another form of dialysis that uses the peritoneum, a membrane in the abdomen, in peritoneal dialysis (PD) to exchange fluid and dissolved materials with the blood. It is used to eliminate extra fluid, address electrolyte imbalances, and eliminate toxins in patients suffering from renal failure.[2]

Dialysis can help the body function when disease or injury prevents kidneys from doing their job as well. When the kidneys only work at 10% to 15% of their normal capacity, renal failure results. Salts and other waste items build up in the blood without dialysis, which can harm other organs.[3]

Patients receiving hemodialysis experience both structural and functional alterations to their cardiovascular systems. Despite advancements in dialysis technology, cardiovascular mortality remains high in this cohort. Many conventional uremic risk factors, especially a chronic uremic state, can impact the cardiovascular system. Many cardiovascular changes, including left ventricular hypertrophy, myocardial fibrosis, accelerated atherosclerosis, and arteriosclerosis, are associated with chronic renal illness.[4]

Patients undergoing hemodialysis have many challenges, which can stem from a range of factors, such as their disease state, food restrictions, psycho-social issues, behavioral issues, or even the process itself. Fatigue is among the most important side effects that hemodialysis patients encounter. Reducing patient weariness is

essential during hemodialysis treatments. Post-dialysis weariness is a common symptom experienced by hemodialysis patients that develops after a treatment session. Patients who had weariness after a dialysis treatment required appropriate care to recuperate since they also experienced bodily aches and trouble sleeping. Additionally, patients' functional independence was limited if they had post-dialysis weariness on the day of treatment. [5]

Fatigue significantly affects a patient's ability to function and their quality of life. It worsens everyday activities, motivation, and social interaction. It also lowers the quality of sleep and exacerbates physical pain. Some data suggest weariness may directly affect clinical outcomes and raise the risk of cardiac arrest and death.[6]

METHODS:

Study Design: True- experimental, parallel group design.

Research Approach: In this study, the researcher used a Quantitative research approach.

Setting: Selected hospitals of the city

Sampling Technique: Probability, simple random sampling technique

Population: Entire group of people or objects or events that all have at least one characteristic in common, regardless of whether it is representative or not, and must be defined precisely and unambiguously; a sample is any part of a population, regardless of whether it is representative or not, and must be defined specifically and unambiguously

DESCRIPTION OF TOOL:

TOOL PREPARATION

A research tool, sometimes known as an instrument, is a device or method that a researcher uses to collect data.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOOL

The development of a tool that provides information and answers to the question under study is the most crucial element of any research. The following instruments are used to obtain data.

Section A - Consent form.

Section B - Structured Interviewing Questionnaire was prepared by the investigator, which include questions regarding demographic variables: Age, Gender, Occupation, Inappropriate habits, Physical activities, Diagnosis, Hemodialysis session in a week, Duration of hemodialysis session.

Section C - A self-structured Fatigue Assessment Scale will be used to measure the level of fatigue.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

1. Approval from the research committee members and written permission from the head of the institution to conduct research were obtained.
2. The purpose of the research was explained to the participants.
3. Informed consent (written) was obtained from the participants.
4. Assessed the level of fatigue in both the experimental groups I and II.
5. Assessed the level of fatigue before giving tap water foot soak and warm water foot soak.
6. Tap water foot soak and warm water foot soak will be given to both experimental groups I and II after 20 mins of hemodialysis session.
7. A foot soak was given for 30 minutes to both experimental groups I and II.
8. Documented the post-intervention level of fatigue in the experimental groups I and II participants after 7 sessions of intervention.
9. Formal permission was obtained from the concerned authority. Subjects were taken from the selected hospitals using the Probability, Simple random sampling technique. The investigators introduced themselves and

informed the samples about the nature of the study to ensure better cooperation during the data collection. The objectives of the study and the confidentiality of the data were discussed.

10. Each subject was given a prepared tool containing.

Section A - Consent form.

Section B - Tool for demographic variable.

Section C - Self-structured fatigue assessment scale was used to measure fatigue.

Steps:

The study was conducted through three phases

a) First phase (Assessment phase)

- All the participants in this study were explained about the nature and purpose of the study.
- All the medical and demographical data was gathered; written consent will be obtained from the participants who are willing to participate in this study.
- The researcher was assessed the patients fatigue level through the self-structured fatigue assessment scale for both experimental groups I and II before interventions.

b) Second phase (Implementing phase)-

1. In this phase the researcher was give tap water and warm water foot soak to the patients after 20 mins of hemodialysis for the period of 30 mins in both experimental groups I and II.
2. For tap water foot soak the researcher was provided plastic basin filled with tap water at temperature of 25⁰C measured by bath thermometer and for warm water foot soak the researcher was provided standardized stainless-steel basin

for foot soak and which was filled with warm water at temperature of 40⁰C measured by bath thermometer. 3. This intervention was done for 7 consecutive sessions

c) Third phase (Evaluation phase)-

The level of fatigue was assessed after 7 consecutive sessions by a self-structured fatigue assessment scale.

Statistical Methods

Descriptive statistics: Frequency and percentage distribution were used to describe demographic variables. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the pre-test and post-test scores.

Inferential statistics: Paired-t test was used to compare the pre-test and post-test Fisher's exact test is used to associate with their selected demographic variables.

DATA ANALYSIS:

SAMPLE SIZE

The formula used for sample size is-

$$n = Z_{\alpha/2}^2 * p * (1-p) / MOE^2$$

n = sample size

$Z_{\alpha/2}$ = Critical value of the Normal distribution at $\alpha/2$

MOE = Margin of error

P = Sample Proportion

For our calculations,

$$Z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96$$

$$P = 0.000129$$

$$MOE = 0.003$$

$$n = (1.96)^2 * 0.000129 * (1 - 0.000129) / (0.003)^2$$

$$n = 3.84 * 0.000129 * 0.999 / 0.000009$$

$$n = 0.000495 / 0.000009$$

n= 55

For the study sample size will be 60, experimental group (n =30) and a control group (n =30).

SAMPLING CRITERIA

Inclusion criteria:

Patients undergoing hemodialysis who are:

- stable on hemodialysis
- Undergoing hemodialysis for at least 1 month
- coming to dialysis 2-3 times a week
- having a fatigue score >10
- able to read and write Marathi and English

Exclusive criteria:

Patients undergoing hemodialysis who are:

- unconscious and terminally ill.
- being absent from 2-3 intervention sessions
- having diabetic foot or amputation of lower extremities.
- Having numbness or loss of sensation or any injury, fracture, or lesion to the lower extremities
- having pyrexia.

RESULT:

Section I: Description of sample based on demographic data.

Age: In the tap water group (experimental group I), 30% of the hemodialysis patients were age 20-30 years, 30% of them were aged 30.1-40 years, 23.3% of them were aged 40.1-50 years, and 16.7% of them had age 50-60 years. In the warm water group (experimental group II), 30% of the hemodialysis patients were aged 20-30 years, 23.3% of them were aged 30.1-40 years, 36.7% of them were aged 40.1-50 years, and 10% of them were aged 50.1-60 years.

Gender: In the tap water group (experimental group I), 50% of them were males and 50% of them were females. In the warm water group (experimental group II),

46.7% of them were males and 53.3% of them were females.

Occupation: In tap water group (experimental group I), 20% of them were private employees and 80% of them were unemployed. In warm water group (experimental group II), 40% of them were private employees, 40% of them were government employees and 20% of them were unemployed.

Personal habits: In the tap water group (experimental group I), 13.3% of them were alcoholic, 6.7% of them were cigarette smokers, 10% of them were tobacco chewers, 50% of them did not have any personal habit, and 20% of them had some other personal habit.

In the warm water Group (experimental group II), 13.3% of them were alcoholic, 6.7% of them were cigarette smokers, 13.3% of them were tobacco chewers, 50% of them did not have any personal habit, and 16.7% of them had some other personal habit.

Healthy habits: In tap water group (experimental group I), 36.7% of them had healthy habits. In warm water group (experimental group II), 40% of them had healthy habits.

Diagnosis: All of them in the tap water and warm water groups had chronic kidney disease.

Hemodialysis session in a week: In tap water (experimental group I) and warm water group (experimental group II), 53.3% of them had 2 hemodialysis sessions per week, and 46.7% of them had 3 dialysis sessions in a week.

Duration of hemodialysis session: In the tap water group (experimental group I), 10% of them had hemodialysis for 1 hour, 20% of them had hemodialysis for 2 hours, 23.3% of them had hemodialysis for 3 hours, 40% of them had dialysis for 4 hours and 6.7% of them had dialysis for 5 hours. In the warm water group (experimental group II), 10% of them had hemodialysis for 1 hour, 20% of them had hemodialysis for 2 hours, 33.3% of them had hemodialysis for 3 hours, 33.3% of them had dialysis for 4 hours and 3.3% of them had dialysis for 5 hours.

Section II : Findings related to the level of fatigue before the implementation of tap water and warm water among patients undergoing hemodialysis at selected hospitals

In Tap water group (experimental group I), 83.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue and 16.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis. In warm water group (experimental group II), 73.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue and 26.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis.

Section III : Findings related to the effectiveness of tap water foot soak on the level of fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis at selected hospitals.

In Tap water group (experimental group I), 83.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue and 16.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis. In posttest, all of them had moderate fatigue after hemodialysis. This indicates that the fatigue among patients improved remarkably after tap water foot soak.

Findings related to effectiveness of warm water foot soak on pretest and post-test level of fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

In warm water group (experimental group II), 73.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue, and 26.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis. In the post-test, 76.7 of them had Moderate fatigue, and 23.3% of them had mild fatigue after hemodialysis. This indicates that the fatigue among patients improved remarkably after a warm water foot soak.

Section IV: Findings related to the paired t-test for the effectiveness of tap water foot soak on the pretest and post-test level of fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

The researcher applied a paired t-test for the effectiveness of tap water foot soak on fatigue among patients after hemodialysis. The average fatigue score in the pretest was 72.7, which was reduced to 66.8 in the posttest. The t-value for this

test was 19.9 with 29 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), so the null hypothesis was rejected. The tap water foot soak is significantly effective in reducing fatigue among patients after hemodialysis.

Findings related to Paired t-test for the effectiveness of warm water foot soak on the fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

The researcher applied a paired t-test for the effectiveness of warm water foot soak on fatigue among patients after hemodialysis. The average fatigue score in the pretest was 71.9, which was reduced to 58.6 in the posttest. The t-value for this test was 24, with 29 degrees of freedom. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The warm water foot soak is significantly effective in reducing fatigue among patients after hemodialysis.

Findings related to two sample z-tests for the comparison of the effectiveness of tap water foot soak and warm water foot soak on fatigue among patients after hemodialysis.

The researcher applied two sample t-tests for the comparison of the effectiveness of warm water foot soak and tap water foot soak on fatigue among patients after hemodialysis. The average reduction in fatigue score in the tap water foot soak group was 5.9, which was 13.4 in the warm water foot soak group. The Z-value for this test was 11.9. The corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), and the null hypothesis was rejected. The average reduction in fatigue score is significantly more in the warm water foot soak group than in the tap water foot soak group. The warm water foot soak is significantly more effective than the tap water foot soak in reducing fatigue among patients after hemodialysis.

Section V: Findings related to the comparison of the effectiveness of tap water foot soak and warm water foot soak on fatigue among patients after hemodialysis.

In Tap water group (experimental group I), 83.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue and 16.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis.

In posttest, all of them had moderate fatigue after hemodialysis.

In warm water group (experimental group II), 73.3% of the hemodialysis patients had moderate fatigue and 26.7% of them had severe fatigue after hemodialysis.

In posttest, 76.7 of them had moderate fatigue and 23.3% of them had mild fatigue after hemodialysis. This indicates that the fatigue among patients improved remarkably after warm water foot soak as compared to tap water.

Section VI

Analysis of data related to the association of fatigue with the selected demographic variable

Fisher's exact test was used for the association between fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis with the demographical variables.

Since p-value corresponding to healthy habits was small (less than 0.05), the demographic variable healthy habits were found to have significant association with the fatigue among hemodialysis patients.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the present study, the investigator suggested the following recommendations.

- A similar study may be replicated on large samples; thereby, findings can be generalized.
- A study to assess the level of fatigue before and after implementation of tap water and warm water foot soak among patients undergoing hemodialysis.
- To assess the effectiveness of tap water and warm water foot soak on the level of fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.
- A similar study can be conducted in different settings, like outpatient clinics and different target populations.
- A similar study can be conducted with different research designs and large samples.

SUMMARY

This chapter dealt with major findings implications, recommendations, and conclusions of effectiveness of intradialytic exercises on selected physiological parameters and fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis at selected hospitals in city.

ABBREVIATIONS:

ADL	Activity Of Daily Living
CI	Confidence Interval
CNG	Control Group
CKD	Chronic Kidney Disease
CVI	Content Validity Index
CRF	Chronic Renal Failure
DBP	Diastolic Blood Pressure
df	Degree Of Freedom
DSI	Dialysis Symptom Index

Table 1: The level of fatigue before implementation of tap water and water foot soak among patients undergoing hemodialysis at selected hospitals.

n=30, 30

Fatigue	Tap water		Warm water	
	Pretest		Pretest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Mild	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Moderate	25	83.3%	22	73.3%
Severe	5	16.7%	8	26.7%

Table 2: Effectiveness of tap water foot soak on fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

n=30, 30

Fatigue	Tap water			
	Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Mild	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Moderate	25	83.3%	30	100.0%
Severe	5	16.7%	0	0.0%

Table 3: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of tap water foot soak on the pretest and posttest level of fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

	Mean	SD	T	df	p-value
Pretest	72.7	6.6	19.9	29	0.000
Posttest	66.8	6.6			

Table 4: Effectiveness of warm water foot soak on fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

n=30

Fatigue	Warm water			
	Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Mild	0	0.0%	7	23.3%
Moderate	22	73.3%	23	76.7%
Severe	8	26.7%	0	0.0%

Table 5: Effectiveness of warm water foot soak on fatigue among patients undergoing hemodialysis.

n=30

Fatigue	Warm water			
	Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Mild	0	0.0%	7	23.3%
Moderate	22	73.3%	23	76.7%
Severe	8	26.7%	0	0.0%

Table 6: Two sample z-tests for the comparison of the effectiveness of tap water foot soak and warm water foot soak on fatigue among patients after hemodialysis

n=30, 30

Group	Mean	SD	z	p-value
Tap water	5.9	1.6	11.9	0.000
Warm water	13.4	3.1		

REFERENCES:

- 1) Cleveland Clinic. Dialysis Information & More [Internet]. Cleveland Clinic. 2021. Available from: <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/treatments/14618-dialysis>
- 2) Wikipedia contributors. Peritoneal dialysis [Internet]. Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia. 2024. Available from: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Peritoneal_dialysis&oldid=1239542483
- 3) Health line. Dialysis: Purpose, Types, Risk and More [Internet]. Health line Available from: <https://www.healthline.com/health/dialysis>
- 4) Chirakarnjanakorn S, Navaneethan SD, Francis GS, Tang WHW. Cardiovascular Impact in Patients Undergoing Maintenance Hemodialysis: Clinical Management Considerations. International journal of cardiology [Internet]. 2017 Apr 1[cited 2021 Jul 11];232:12–23. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5316356/>
- 5) Horigan AE. Fatigue in Hemodialysis Patients: A Review of Current Knowledge. Journal of Pain and Symptom Management. 2012 Nov;44(5):715–24.
- 6) Picariello, F., Moss-Morris, R., Macdougall, I. C., & Chilcot, J. (2016). The role of psychological factors in fatigue among end-stage kidney disease patients: A critical review Clinical Kidney Journal, sfw113.